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CHALLENGES OF ONLINE TEACHING FOR TEACHERS IN THE PHILIPPINES

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Online teaching was not that common during pre-pandemic, but it has been around since the early 1900s. Due to the pandemic in 2020, teachers and students were forced to adapt to this kind of learning setup. People were prohibited from leaving their homes for everyone's safety. That means activities that used to do outside, such as working and studying, should be done at home. People must learn to accept and adapt to some changes to survive and live.

Students shared their struggles on various social media platforms when online classes began. Majority of the complaints center around the lack of a mobile device and a dependable internet connection for studying. Some students could not afford to have the internet at home, especially in a middle of a crisis where food is more important than web access. The number of learners who dropped out did not decrease despite the Department of Education lending the students tablets they could use for distance learning.

The Department of Education provided laptops for teachers to utilize for online instruction. The government provided them with almost everything they needed, but it did not change the fact that studying and teaching online remained difficult. In 2020, a large number of teachers in the Philippines chose to resign. Carissa Nanagas Encarnacion, a former educator who resigned in 2020, shared in her blog the reason for her early retirement. Teachers were supposed to go to school and prepare the modules that students would use in their online classes. She noted that even if the school takes all necessary safety procedures, there is no assurance that the transportation from home to school will also be secure. For elderly teachers, the internet setup can be challenging. They must learn how to use the technology, which is tough for someone with no experience. Unfortunately, some students choose to neglect rather than assist these struggling professors, taking advantage of their cluelessness.

Teaching during the pandemic was difficult, but it was also distressing to think if the students were learning anything because no one knows what they do behind the screen. Some students have been caught by their teachers engaging in unnecessary activities like playing mobile games in class. It is frustrating to know that all of your efforts went to nothing because your students are not interested to learn. Lesson preparation takes some time to complete, and it is disheartening for them that the students do not

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recognize their efforts despite the trying times. But of course, teachers must not get undetermined with this. Some students are still willing to learn regardless of what the setup is. All the sacrifices of the teachers for the sake of teaching the future of this world will be worth it once they become the person they aspire to become.

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